

HYDROXYPROPYL METHYLCELLULOSE AND SILVER NANOPARTICLES BASED ON ANTIBACTERIAL HYDROGELS

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Annotation. The progress achieved in recent years in the biomedical field justifies the objective evaluation of new techniques and materials obtained by using silver in different forms as metallic silver, silver salts, and nanoparticles. Thus, the antibacterial, antiviral, antifungal, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory activity of silver nanoparticles confers to newly obtained materials characteristics that make them ideal candidates in a wide spectrum of applications. Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose is routinely used for the controlled release of medicine thanks to its slow dissolution in water and could be used as a matrix for the controlled release of silver nanoparticles, if a method to produce such a material without the need of other reactants was developed. We proposed such a method in a photochemical reduction of AgNO_3 in hydroxypropyl methylcellulose solutions by the illumination of the mixture with the UV irradiation.

Keywords. Silver nanoparticles, hydroxypropylmethylcellulose, photochemical synthesis.

The medical field is faced with various infectious diseases triggered by germs (bacteria, viruses, fungi and protozoa), associated with microbial resistance. This is the main reason for the current intense research into antibacterial agents. In addition, microorganisms which contaminate the surfaces of medical devices in hospitals have led to development of antimicrobial surfaces based on polymers as a necessary tool to combat microbial infections and prevent the spread of microbial cells [1]. In this context, polymeric materials, due to their intrinsic properties, e.g., their hydrophilicity or molecular weight, have gained an increasing interest from both academic and industrial perspectives. Thus, systems based on the combination of polymer and inorganic/organic antimicrobial agents present a special interest. In this regard, the improvement of the antimicrobial activity and the reduction in the toxicity will be ensured by the incorporation of the antimicrobial agent. Based on the various studies presented in the literature [2]. Silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) are an intensively studied material due to their unique antibacterial properties combined with relatively low production costs. These particular properties predetermine the AgNPs for applications in areas such as functional textiles, active food packaging, medicine, cosmetics, ecology [3]. In cosmetics, AgNPs have recently been used as additives for their antiseptic. Active food packaging is an innovative concept where the container interacts with the enclosed product and the surrounding environment to preserve the quality of the product during prolonged storage. AgNPs supported on graphene oxide were infused into polyviscose pads to form antibacterial functional textile. In medicine, AgNPs can be used in diagnosis or directly for treatment as topical antimicrobial agents, wound dressing, implants or for cancer treatment. On the other hand, high concentrations of silver induce cytotoxicity and lead to argyria due to inappropriate silver accumulation in blood, lungs, liver and kidneys.

AgNPs can be prepared by a variety of methods, but for colloids of monodisperse nanoparticles (NPs), the chemical reduction of Ag salts is the most common approach. Standard approaches utilize strong reducing agents such as NaBH_4 , which are great for the highly controlled production of small monodisperse of NPs; however, a lot of attention was recently directed towards the use of less toxic alternatives, which are more desirable for medicinal purposes, due to the residues of the reducing and stabilizing agents being non-toxic. Commonly used reactants include proteins such as collagen, gelatin or keratin and polysaccharides such as chitosan and cellulose. Polysaccharides can also serve as stabilization agents, which enables the simple preparation of solid form NPs composites by evaporating the solvent. Another way to eliminate

the need for additional reaction agents is employing physicochemical methods of silver nitrate reduction. Because silver nitrate is very sensitive to visible light, it is possible to induce its reduction by the illumination of its solution in a photochemical reduction process.

Cellulose-based materials are important for this purpose due to the properties they possess, such as biocompatibility, barrier properties, non-polluting, lack of toxicity, and low-cost. However, the cellulose derivatives, as result of the chemical modifications, tend to improve the cellulose backbone in terms of solubility, viscosity, and film-forming performance [4]. Notably, hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC) is an attractive polymer that can be used for wider applications in the biomedical field because it is a readily available non-ionic plant derivative that forms transparent, flexible, water-soluble films with efficiency in oxygen and carbon dioxide transport.

The aim this work is the study of possibility to formation of AgNPs in HPMC solutions by ultraviolet irradiation based on antibacterial hydrogel and study their physico-chemical properties.

Silver colloids were prepared by photochemical method with hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC) serving as a capping agent. First, solutions of HPMC were prepared by the mixing of 12.5, 25 or 50 mg of HPMC powder, viscosity 0.8–0.12 Pa·s in 2% water at 20 °C and 45 mL of distilled water and the mixture was stirred in refrigerator overnight. Then, 5 mL of 35 mM solution of AgNO₃ was added dropwise to the HPMC solution at constant stirring in a shaded Erlenmeyer flask. The resulting mixture was therefore 3.5 mmol·L⁻¹ AgNO₃ in 0.25%, 0.5% or 1% HPMC solution. Temperature was brought up to 25 °C and the solution was stirred further for 30 min. During this process, Ag seeds were created that catalyzed the photochemical reduction of the AgNO₃ in the next preparation step. Photochemical reduction of Ag⁺ in HPMC to generate NPs was performed at 25°C by irradiation with a DRSh-250 high-pressure mercury vapour lamp (wattage = 35 watts and wavelength $\lambda = 365$ nm). To obtain dispersions of HPMC/AgNPs, a UZDN-1 ultrasonic disperser (Y-4.2, Russia), was used.

The solution was irradiated for 30 minutes while its appearance changed from transparent colorless to dark yellow to reddish brown with apparent turbidity.

The structure, size and polydispersity of the prepared AgNPs was studied by DLS, which showed the rather wide size distribution of the prepared AgNPs. Most of the particles were found to be smaller than 100 nm in diameter. This has an effect on other parameters of the colloids, and the UV-Vis spectra showed broad absorbances with dipole and quadrupole oscillations. In order to improve the size distribution and control of AgNPs, the proposed preparation procedure and conditions should be further investigated, because compared to HPMC photochemically reduced AgNPs, the size distribution of AgNPs was much wider. Obtained bactericidal hydrogel, contained stable AgNPs can be used for the treatment of burns and wounds.

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